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ELECTROCARDIOGRAPHY AND ITS APPLICATION METHODS

Abstract. *This article provides an understanding of the history of ECG recording and its foundations, as well as its global importance in heart diseases. The importance of ECG in the clinical diagnosis of heart patients is discussed. Today, heart-related diseases are on the rise in our country. The increasing number of heart diseases and the importance of ECG in it became the basis for them to know that even some heart diseases (myocardial infarction, angina pectoris) can be diagnosed by ECG.*

Keywords: *biopotentials, classical, anterior, dorsal, AVR, AYL.*

Electrocardiogram (electrocardiogram) (ECG) is a recording of the electrical impulses produced by the heart muscle. E. is recorded on paper or photographic film using an electrocardiograph. Heart currents spreading throughout the body (motor currents) ECG are recorded by electrodes placed on different parts of the body (chest, arms and legs) and connected to an electrocardiograph. Modern medical technology makes it possible to record an EKG even if the patient is at a great distance using television or radio transmitters. Such methods make it possible to monitor the heart activity of athletes, astronauts and others during severe physical tests. Electrocardiography is a method based on the graphic recording of biopotentials that occur when the heart contracts

Graphic pictures taken by electrocardiography method electrocardiogram (ECG)

ECG can be obtained using standard and chest methods.

Standard method: in this method, electrodes can be placed on the following parts of the body in three different combinations.

ПЕДАГОГИКА И ПСИХОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКИЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ

1. In the standard method, the electrodes are placed on the lower part of the right and left wrists.

2. In the standard method, it is placed on the lower part of the wrist of the right hand and the lower part of the calf of the left leg.

3. In the standard method, it is placed on the lower part of the left wrist and the lower part of the left leg.

Weaning techniques: these techniques are usually denoted by the letter V (Wilson).

One electrode is left on the hand, and the other electrode is placed on the following points of the body.

V1 - to the right edge of the sternum between the 4 ribs.

V2 - 4 to the left edge of the sternum of the intercostal space.

V3 - to the middle of the distance between the places indicated in methods V2 and V4.

V4 - the length between the fifth ribs to the left (lin. medioclavicularis sin).

V5 - from the axillary line between the 5th ribs (lin. axillaries anterior sin) on the left side.

V6 - from the middle axillary line between the 5 ribs (lin. Axillaries media) from the left side.

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As soon as the current movement is formed, characteristic curves are formed

Positive looking up from the isoline: R, P, T downward facing negative two prongs Q, S. During the period of relaxation of the heart (diastole), current movements are not formed, and the electrocardiograph device records the correct, i.e., isoelectric line.

Sinus tachycardia: occurs when the heart beats from 90-120 to 150. This condition occurs after strong excitement, hard work, and heart defects.

Sinus bradycardia:

It occurs in healthy people under the influence of cold weather, or in those who practice sports regularly. Sinus bradycardia occurs in cases of brain tumors, meningitis, increased intracranial pressure, and some types of myocardial infarction.

What is the purpose of an electrocardiogram (ECG)?

An electrocardiogram allows a cardiologist to identify a number of heart diseases and pathologies, including:

-arrhythmias: changes in heart rhythm: the heart beats irregularly, too slowly or too fast. The diagnosis of arrhythmias is very important because they are often asymptomatic and can lead to cardiac arrest and sudden death;

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-ischemia and/or infarction: An EKG can detect cardiac activity caused by reduced blood flow to the heart (ischemia) due to narrowing of the coronary arteries, which can lead to myocardial infarction (death of heart tissue);

Congenital or acquired changes and physical disorders in the heart cavity, such as valvulopathies, ventricular hypertrophy, dilated cardiomyopathies, etc.;

-electrolyte disorders: excessive or low concentration of blood electrolytes that cause changes in heart rhythm;

-toxic effects of some drugs: can cause heart muscle damage.

References:

- 1 Propedevtika vnutrennix bolezney" Grebnev A.L., Moscow 2001,
2. "Propedevtika vnutrennix bolezney" Mukhin N.A., Moiseev V.S., Moscow 2002.
- 3 "Propedevtika vnutrennix bolezney" V.Kh. Vasilenko, 1995.
- 4 "Propaedeutics of internal diseases" E.Y. Kosimov, Sh.G. Mukminova, 5 N.B. Nuriddinov, Tashkent 1996.
- "Propaedeutics of internal diseases"
- 6 M.N. Koraboeva and others; Tashkent 1996.

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